

Mystery of Suffering Unravels the Mystery of God's Faithfulness

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God so loved the world that He gave his only Son, so that everyone who believes in Him may not perish but may have eternal life (Jn.3:16). Yes, out of His love He reconciled the fallen humankind through His Son Emmanuel 'God with us.' Jesus is always with us as mystic Meister Eckhart says: "Man goes far away or near but God never goes off. He is always standing close at hand and even if he cannot stay within, he goes no further than the door."

Suffering as Inevitable

Right from the beginning, suffering has become the subject of heated discussion, argumentation and meditation. Almost all religions try to explain the cause of suffering and offer ways and means to respond to it. At present, we are suffering physically, mentally and psychologically, especially due to the outbreak of the pandemic Coronavirus. It has infected millions of people all over the world. Many lost their loved ones unexpectedly. In order to stop the spread of the Covid-19 many countries have been put under strict lockdown which has destroyed the economic growth and separated many from their dear ones. It has created fear, anxiety and restlessness in humanity. In such times of trial and suffering, sometimes we are tempted to lose our faith and hope in life. We often grapple with basic questions like: Does God really exist? Does he really love

186

the world? We forget everything, His merciful love and our life as a gift from God and sometimes even think of end one's life. Suffering cannot be explained fully with human intellect. However, there remains the possibility of accepting it as an inevitable part of human life and then to transform and integrate it into human life.

According to philosopher Viktor Frankl, one can find meaning to suffering. He says that suffering ceases to be suffering in some way to the moment it finds a meaning. Such as the meaning of a sacrifice. One of the greatest gifts faith in God offers us is a sense of meaning that transcends the ups and downs of life, and that meaning gives birth to hope.

Frankl claims that there are three main avenues on which one arrives at meaning in life. The first is by creating a work or doing a deed. Secondly, by experiencing something or encountering someone: in other words, meaning can be found not only in works but also in love. Thirdly, even the helpless victim of a hopeless situation, facing a fate one cannot change, may rise above oneself, may grow beyond oneself and by so doing change oneself (Frankl 2000). If there is a meaning in life at all, then there must be a meaning in suffering. Suffering is an inevitable part of life, even as fate and death. Without suffering and death, human life cannot be complete. We can look at sufferings in many ways. Some suffering makes it possible for us to feel compassion for others who are victimized and suffer innocently. Suffering can also be for our purification. As the Scripture says "See, I have refined you, but not like silver; I have tested you in the furnace of adversity" (Is 48:10).

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187

Suffering as Lived Mystery

Some suffering enables us to follow Christ crucified closely because he himself promised, "If any want to become my followers, let them deny themselves and take up their daily cross and follow me" (Mt 16:24). Some pains, like the loss of our beloved ones, make us realize that none of us are indispensable in this world. Such experiences also teach us how little sovereignty we have over our lives. In this way, pain contributes to human solidarity.

Ultimately suffering is a mystery and God is the fellow sufferer. Cardinal Luis Antonio Tagle (2018) in his book *The Risk of Hope* tells one of his experiences. He met a man whose sister was raped some years ago. The man was very angry with God and said, I do not understand why God allowed this to happen. Why was God not able to rescue my sister? Why did he not help my sister? In prayer God replied him. How could I have helped your sister? I was also suffering with her; she was not the only victim. I was a victim like her torn and unjustly treated. We can also recall the famous poem "Footprints in the Sand," where the person questioned God when she/he saw in times of difficulty that only one set of footprints on the sand, God replied "during your times of trial and suffering, when you see only one set of footprints, it was then that I carried you." It invites us to face difficulties with courage without losing hope.

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188

However, Christianity becomes meaningful, enlightening and consoling when it comes to the question of suffering because a Christian God manifested in Jesus Christ has understood very well the mystery of human suffering. As a result, He is not a God who looks at suffering from far but becomes co-

sufferer. He knows what is pain, hunger, thirst, loneliness rejection and finally, death. He is not just a pure act, unmoved mover, or an infinite being. These are philosophical concepts, but He is much more than that. Therefore, it is easy for us to establish a relationship with him, to pray to him, to go to him when we suffer. We will find more solace and comfort in a God who suffers with us and for us. By saying this, I do not mean that we should glorify suffering. Some of the physical and mental sufferings are so destructive that one cannot justify them. We need to remain silent in the face of such pain, because suffering is not the end. For Christ Crucifixion is not the end of the story, but it leads to Resurrection.

Conclusion

Our lady of Lourdes said to St. Bernadette, “I cannot promise happiness in this life but in the next life.” We find in the gospel the miserable life of Lazarus who suffered a lot, but when he died, he was placed at the side of Abraham (Lk 16:23). Therefore, each of our pains and sufferings has something to offer us, so let us join with the suffering of Christ and endure it.

In our journey we are not alone but Immanuel God is with us. Let us be sure of His faithfulness, for if we are faithless, He remains faithful, for He cannot deny Himself (2 Tim 2:13).

Reference

Frankl, Viktor E. *Man's Search for Meaning: An Introduction to Logotherapy*. New York: Houghton, Mifflin, 2000

Tagle, Luis A. *The Risk of Hope: How to Talk About God in the World Today*. Maryknoll : Orbis Books, 2018.